

Rethinking Materials for Buildings: Exploration of plastic bottles as construction material

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ABSTRACT: The present study aims to explore the potential of plastic bottles as construction material focusing on the structural systems of the construction. This research was motivated by the increasing concern for plastic waste and pollution, that threatens human health and ecosystems, and seeks a solution to this plastic waste problem by identifying the feasible construction methods utilizing plastic bottles. To achieve this research goal, a systematic review of literature and projects was conducted, and an educational activity was developed based on the review. In the educational activity, eleven teams of two students worked on a plastic bottle chair project utilizing various construction methods and complementary materials. The project outcome showed the good potential of plastic bottles as construction materials and the bottles may be used without infilling materials if a proper system for structural connection and support can be developed. The significance of this study is the effort to introduce plastic bottles and the supporting systems as general construction materials, and the methodology that reviews multiple cases rather than a single project. The contribution of this study is promoting circular material cycle and affordable construction utilizing this "low tech - high impact" process.

KEYWORDS: Recycle, Plastic bottle, PET, Chair, Construction

1. INTRODUCTION

Increasing plastic waste and pollution have become a major concern recently, threatening human health and ecosystems. According to UNESCO, about 80% of marine pollution is plastic waste (Figure 1), which affects around 17% of marine species [16]. Although the production of plastic in the last ten years outweighs the production in the previous century, which may triple the amount of plastic waste in oceans by 2040, only 10% of the current plastic waste is being recycled [15-16]. The negative impacts of plastic waste have been widely known, such as the contamination of the environment, air pollution from uncontrolled incineration, and food contamination for wildlife and human beings [18].

Figure 1: About 80% of marine pollution is plastic waste (source: Science Photo Library, CC BY-NC).

Responding to these issues, Fischer and Kowalski (1998) stated that the material cycle loop should be

closed by utilizing wastes as material resources [3]. Also, Braungart and McDonough (2022) mentioned that the zero-waste design with a circular approach should be part of green city planning [7]. One of the effective ways of participating in these zero-waste efforts in the building industry would be increasing recycled materials for construction, which may reduce the need for new materials and processing [11].

This paper particularly focuses on plastic bottles, one of the most used items in the world, exploring their potential as construction materials through a literature review and educational activities under the following research question: how plastic bottles can be assembled while gaining the required structural capacity for construction? The effort to identify the prototypes and generalize the findings based on multiple projects rather than focusing on a single project as a one-time event may be the significance of this study, which would help further dissemination of the construction using plastic bottles.

2. BACKGROUND

As the problem of plastic waste and pollution has been exacerbated, researchers and educators have tried to find a solution by utilizing plastic bottles for design and building material studies. Lalarliana, Lalngaihawmaa, and Sainia (2018) emphasized the growing concerns about the demolition wastes of concrete constructions and plastic wastes and proposed a combination of these two materials, plastic bottles filled with crushed concrete aggregates, as construction materials. By testing different mixing

ratios, they found that 5% was the optimal water content for compressive strength.

Nováková, Šepsb, and Achtena (2017) developed a recycled product, PET(b)rick, focusing on the stacking feature and blow-molding technology of the recycled plastic material. By testing the structural performance of the materials, they found that the proposed material has sufficient resistance to stress, pressure, heat, and freezing to be a fill-in material if an appropriate medium can be filled with an appropriate amount. They also claimed that exhibiting designs made of recycled materials, such as PET(b)rick, may have a social impact appealing to others to think further about plastic waste problems and actions they can do [11].

Mansour and Ali (2015) also conducted experiments focusing on the infill materials to investigate and compare the structural and thermal performance of plastic bottles filled with different materials. Their study results indicated that plastic bottle blocks have a good structural capacity for partition walls or bearing walls for one roof slab. The study also found that the thermal capacity of air-filled bottles was higher compared to dry or saturated sand-filled bottles or conventional block construction, which shows the potential of plastic bottles as thermal insulation material [6].

Haque and Islam (2021) focused on the application of the plastic bottle brick that they developed in the Rohingya displacement camps in Bangladesh, which is the largest refugee camp in the world. The current shelters in the camps are not resistant enough to natural disasters in the region, thus, the refugees in the camps suffer from unstable and unhygienic living conditions. The authors developed a plastic brick system utilizing plastic bottle wastes to provide an affordable solution to this problem. In this system, the bottles were filled with sand and placed at the center of the cardboard-framed brick. The space between the bottle and frame was filled with hand-blended mortar, which helped gain the structural capacity to resist extreme weather conditions [5].

In addition to the aforementioned research, artistic installations and projects have been also performed by various designers and artists. For example, Archtech S.r.l. built Two-O-Four Chair in Trento, Italy [13]. This chair design emphasizes the transparency of the chair by using transparent plastic bottles and lighting. Similarly, Pawel Grunert exhibited the SIE43 Chair in Milan, Italy [17]. This project uses a metal frame to support plastic bottles and create the wave shape of the chair. Also, Varnai Gyula displayed an installation artwork, Giant Armchair, in Budapest, Hungary utilizing 2,500 plastic bottles stacked with packing tapes [9]. Different from other projects, the Human-Computer Interaction Lab at the Hasso Plattner

Institute in Potsdam, Germany, focused on the connector design of plastic-bottle truss structures [2].

While the reviewed research achieved the structural strength of plastic bottles for construction by studying the performance of infill materials and filling the bottles with the materials, the reviewed artworks used various connectors and framing systems for stability and strength. Although many similar studies and projects are found in the literature, most studies tend to focus on one project rather than comparing multiple projects and identifying prototypes. Also, not many studies on stacking and connecting systems for plastic bottles are available. The present study aims to fill this knowledge gap and identify stack and connection prototypes for construction with plastic bottles.

3. METHODOLOGY

The present study employed a qualitative case study approach that allows an empirical, holistic, and multifaceted investigation in a real-world setting [41014]. To perform the study, relevant literature and existing projects were first reviewed, then, a design-build project for an architecture course was developed based on the review. The course was an elective for 4th and 5th year undergraduate students and graduate students about sustainability. In the proposed design-build project, each group had two students to design and build a one-to-one scale chair made of recycled plastic bottles. Although students could choose the materials for stacking and connecting the bottles, only recycled or biodegradable material options were allowed. The project poster had to describe the material selection process, design concept, and construction process, such as sketches, diagrams, and photos of the testing and making processes. For example, a group presented a photo of an experiment to compare the structural capacity of different plastic bottles to explain their material selection processes (Figure 2). Another group presented their construction process and explained how a truss structure could become a support for the seat (Figure 3).

The evaluation criteria of the project were *Material selection*, *Structural stability*, *Efficiency*, *Comfort*, and *Creativity*. In the *Material selection* criterion, the primary material should be plastic bottles or jars, while other recycled or biodegradable materials should be complementary for structural support. In the *Structural stability* criterion, the load-bearing capacity of the chair should be a minimum of 200 lb (91 kg). In the *Efficiency* criterion, the making process should be short and simple enough to easily assemble and disassemble the chair. In the *Comfort* criterion, the ergonomics of the chair were evaluated, such as the chair dimensions, including the height, compared to average human body sizes. In the *Creativity* criterion, creative and innovative design that experiments with

a unique and novel chair form and structure received additional points.

Figure 2: Material selection process of a project – comparing the structural capacity of a water bottle and a sports drink bottle to explain the team’s material finding process (source: Gabe DeLiberty, Leah LeBlanc).

Figure 3: Construction process of a project – utilizing truss structure for the support (source: Omid Elhami, Maryam Sinejani).

After the evaluation of the projects, the structural materials and design approach of each team were analyzed and compared to categorize the information. This result was compared to the referenced projects and literature. Figure 4 summarizes the process of this study.

Figure 4: Process of the present study.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A total of eleven chairs were designed and built as an outcome of this project. Plastic bottles of different types and sizes were used for the project, such as water bottles and jars, other drink bottles, and milk jars. Some projects actively utilized the colors of the bottles to achieve the color scheme of the team’s design (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Made of sports drink bottles, biodegradable tapes, and packaging boxes. The colors of the bottles were actively utilized to achieve the color scheme of the design (source: Gabe DeLiberty, Leah LeBlanc).

For structural connections and supports, wrapping, framing, filling, and weaving were the primary methods. Employed materials for the project were as follows: boxes, edge protectors for packaging, twine, soil and gravel, plastic wraps, and plastic bags. Some projects added non-structural materials, including newspapers and plants, to improve the comfort and sitting experience for the users. Table 1 shows the various construction strategies of the chairs completed in this project. It should be noted that some materials minimally used in the project were not counted in this categorization. Also, the total number of teams in the table exceeds 11 due to the teams employing multiple methods and materials.

Table 1: Construction and material strategies of the plastic bottle chair projects.

Projects	Primary material	Supporting material	Construction methodology
1	Milk jar	Plastic wrap	Wrapping
2	Water bottles and jars	Twine	Weaving
3	Water bottles	Edge protectors, screws	Framing
4	Sports drink bottles	Boxes, tapes	Framing
5	Water bottles	Plastic bags, newspapers	Weaving
6	Water bottles and large drink bottles	Yarn, plastic wrap	Weaving and wrapping
7	Water bottles	Plastic wrap, boxes, newspapers	Wrapping and framing
8	Water bottles	Wood bars, tapes	Wrapping and framing
9	Water bottles	Twine, plants, boxes, water, clothes	Weaving, framing, filling
10	Water bottles and jars, large drink bottles	Plastic wrap, boxes	Wrapping and filling
11	Water bottles	Twine, boxes	Weaving and wrapping

The distribution of structural approach in this project was as follows:

- Wrapping – 6 teams
- Framing – 5 teams
- Weaving – 5 teams
- Filling – 2 teams

The distribution of structural framing and connection materials in this project was as follows:

- Boxes – 5 teams
- Plastic wrap – 4 teams
- Twine – 3 teams
- Tapes – 2 teams
- Edge protectors – 1 team
- Plastic bags – 1 team

Figures 6 - 8 show the example projects that employed wrapping, framing, and weaving methods respectively.

Figure 6: Made of milk jars and used plastic wraps. Primary construction method is wrapping (source: Adeyinka Ariwajoye, Nicole Jacobo).

Figure 7: Made of water bottles and used edge protectors. Primary construction method is framing with edge protectors and screws (source: Omid Elhami, Maryam Sinejani).

Figure 8: Made of twine, water bottles and jars. Primary construction method is weaving (source: Jiahui Li, Sanaz Salajegheh).

The result of this study showed that plastic bottle chairs could gain the required structural strength without filling the bottle with additional materials other than air if a proper support or stacking system can be developed. This may be the reason that not many students chose to use filling compared to wrapping, framing, and weaving. The most preferred material for structural support was boxes due to the easy access to the material. Plastic wraps were also used by four teams claiming that those materials were recycled or biodegradable. Twines and tapes were purchased materials, but biodegradable products. Not many groups chose to use edge protectors for their structural materials, but many noted them as promising materials since they are often used for packaging. Plastic bags were all recycled and easy to access, however, the processing time for using the bags as connectors was longer than other methods.

The most challenging part of the project was supporting the seat at an appropriate height. Except for specific design concepts that require a low height, a comfortable height, which is around 16 – 18" (400 – 450mm), had to be provided for the seat. Students who did not use a framing system for the support had to find plastic bottles with the right size and structural strength, and a good assembly method that could achieve the required height and support the required structural load. Another challenge that the project teams faced was the controversy about the sustainability of the connection and support materials.

Although plastic and metal products for structural connections, such as plastic wraps, plastic bags, and edge protectors, were recycled materials from other packages, they are not biodegradable, and their availability may be discontinuous. These issues can make the sustainability of structural materials questionable. Despite the challenges, the completed chair project showed the potential of plastic bottles as construction materials for indoor environments and identified various feasible construction approaches.

5. CONCLUSION

The present study was motivated by the increasing concern about plastic waste and pollution and tried to find a solution to this problem by exploring the potential of plastic bottles as a construction material. Questioning the structural connection and stability of the construction using plastic bottles, existing research and some design-build projects were reviewed. Based on the review, a plastic bottle chair project was developed in an elective course for upper-level undergraduate and graduate students in an architecture program. In this project, eleven teams of two students designed and built one-to-one scale chairs made of plastic bottles experimenting with various assembly methods. The project outcomes showed that providing a framing system to stack and support plastic bottles was the most preferred structural solution by the designers, and the boxes were the most popular material for the support. The small sample size would be the limitation of this study; thus, further studies are necessary to generalize these findings.

The present study may contribute to minimizing plastic waste by reclaiming plastic bottles as construction material that may help create a circular material cycle loop. In addition to this environmental contribution, the present study may promote more affordable design using plastic bottles that do not require specialized knowledge to build, in other words, a low-tech, but bringing a high impact [12]. The case study and comparative analysis approach of this research investigating multiple projects may be helpful in generalizing the findings and identifying the prototypes of the construction with plastic bottles. Finally, introducing further studies on recycled materials in architectural education may contribute to the dissemination of recycled materials in the building industry. Inviting students, who are future professionals, to the ongoing discussions on plastic waste and pollution and how to collaborate with others to solve these issues, may lead to a broader impact of the study. Future research can be continued to further projects and courses for expanding the sample size. Also, the scale of the design-build projects can be enlarged to walls or pavilions to expand the structural challenges and discussions.

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